

A Comparative Study of Autologous Blood versus Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery for Pterygium

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Abstract:

Background: Pterygium is a pink fleshy sub conjunctival growth that covers the white part of your eye over the cornea.

Aim: To Compare the Autologous Blood versus Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery for Pterygium.

Materials and Methods: 30 patients attending Ophthalmology OPD with primary pterygium were randomised into two groups of 15 patients in each group by a simple randomisation technique. Patients were divided into two groups and undergoing pterygium excision followed by conjunctival autografting either by patient's own blood (group A) or by suture (group B).

Results: Males were more affected by pterygium as compared to females. The mean age of the patient in group A was 43.6 and in group B was 46.86. The duration of surgery in group A was 21.33 min and in group B was 35.5 min. No recurrence was observed at day 90 in both groups.

Conclusion: Conjunctival autografting by patient's own blood is better than suture.

Keywords: Pterygium, Autologous Blood, Autograft Surgery, Pain, Itching, Watering, F.B. Sensation, Inflammation, Graft Displacement.

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Introduction

The word pterygium derived from a Greek word "Pterygos" which means "wing". Pterygium is a degenerative condition of subconjunctival tissue characterised by a triangular portion of the bulbar conjunctiva encroaching onto the cornea [1]. It is slightly vascular and seen in the interpalpebral fissure in the horizontal meridian. Most often from the nasal side. It invades the cornea destroying the superficial layers of the stroma and Bowman's membrane [2]. A unique feature of pterygium epithelial cell is its positive immune- histochemical staining for different types of metalloproteinases that are absent in normal conjunctival, limbal or corneal cells [3].

The surgery is indicated for Cosmetic Reason Involvement of visual axis Induced Astigmatism. To prevent recurrence, adjunctive therapies are considered which reduces recurrence rate significantly. These include application of Mitomycin C, radiotherapy, conjunctival or limbal conjunctival autograft (CAG), and amniotic membrane graft [4]. Traditionally, Pterygium surgery with CAG used sutures to secure the autograft in place. The use of fibrin glue for this purpose was popularised by V Koranyi et al in 2004 [5, 6]. Replacing the sutures with adhesives

decreased the operating time, improved post-operative comfort. But the major problem with fibrin glue is the cost and potential risk of transmitted infection (Human immunodeficiency virus, Parvo virus B19, Hepatitis) [7].

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted at Department of Ophthalmology of IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India. The Study was conducted over a period from September 2019 to November 2020.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who were diagnosed with primary pterygium and met the indication for surgical treatment
- Patients aged between 20 to 60 years
- Patients having pterygium covering more than 2mm of cornea.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient having age less than 20 years and more than 60 years Pterygium less than 2 mm of cornea
- Patients who had glaucoma in the study eye

- Patients who had an intraocular pressure >21mm Hg
- Patients who had a history of allergy to steroid eye drops
- Recurrent pterygium
- Pseudo pterygium
- Pregnant women
- Ocular surface disorder, infection and any trauma

30 patients attending Ophthalmology OPD with primary pterygium in the study period and accepted in the inclusion criteria will comprise the study population. The patients were randomised into two groups of 15 patients in each group by a simple randomisation technique. After detailed ocular and systemic history, a thorough ocular examination including visual acuity, refraction and slit-lamp examination was done. Hematological examination such as Hemoglobin (Hb), Bleeding Time (BT) and clotting time (CT) were performed in each patient. All cases were operated using surgical microscope under aseptic conditions and managed on an outpatient basis.

Patients were divided into two groups and undergoing pterygium excision followed by conjunctival autografting either by patient's own blood (group A) or by suture (group B). Various parameters like operating time (starting from placement of lid speculum to its removal at the end of surgery) as well as postoperative symptoms, signs were noted for both the groups. Follow up was done on postoperative day 1, 8, 30, 90 and 180. During each postoperative visit, slit-lamp examination, the acceptance of the graft and any suture related complications were checked.

Results and Discussion

The present prospective study compared the Autologous Blood versus Conventional Conjunctival Autograft Surgery for Pterygium. A total of 30 patients divided randomly into two groups were evaluated. The result of the study showed, out of 30 patients in our study 20 were males and 10 were females (Fig-1).

Figure 1: Sex Distribution

Our study shows that males were more affected by pterygium as compared to females. We found a greater number of patients at the old age group. Out of 30 patients, 22 patients had 3 to 4 mm involvement of cornea. The mean age of the patient in group A was 43.6 and in group B was 46.86. The duration of surgery in group A was 21.33 min and in group B was 35.5 min which is significantly higher compared to group A. We compared all the symptoms (e. g. Pain, Itching, Watering, F.B.

Sensation, Graft displacement, Subgraft Haem' G, Inflammation) of patients of Group A and Group B. p value <0.5 is considered significant.

On Postoperative Day 1

On postoperative day 1, among all the postoperative signs and symptoms, the p-value for watering, itching and graft displacement is significantly high and for pain is also significant as compared to Group B (Fig- 2).

Figure 2: Comparison of Groups A and B (On postoperative day 1)

On Postoperative Day 8

On postoperative day 8, among all the postoperative signs and symptoms, the p-value for watering, itching and inflammation is significantly high as compared to Group B. In group A, pain was

absent on post operative day 8 and the difference between the two groups was statistically significant. Whereas Graft displacement is significantly high in Group B as compared to Group A. There was no case of F.B. Sensation and Subgraft Haem'G on Day 8 (Fig 3).

Fig 3: Comparison of Groups A and B (On postoperative day 8)

On Postoperative Day 30

On Postoperative Day 30, among all the postoperative signs and symptoms only watering, itching and inflammation were still present. The recurrence of pterygium is studied at day 90 and

day 180 postoperatively. No recurrence was observed at day 90 in both groups. On day 180, Group B showed a recurrence whereas no recurrence was seen in Group A.

Fig 4: Comparison of Groups A and B (On postoperative day 30)

Conclusion

In our study, mean operative time for group A was significantly less as compared to patients of group B. Pain subsides completely on postoperative day 8 in patient's own blood group while in group B, it subsides completely on day 30.

On day 30 watering, itching and irritation were still presents in both groups. But in group B, these were statistically high as compared to own blood group. There was a recurrence in group B. Conjunctival autografting by patient's own blood is better than suture as:

Less operative time, less postoperative ocular signs and symptoms, better patient comfort, economical, no recurrence, absence of potential adverse reaction caused due to use of foreign material.

References

1. Sangole AM, Kose DA. A comparative study between surgical outcome of patients own blood vs. 10-0 nylon for conjunctival autografting in pterygium excision. *J. Evid. Based Med. Healthc.* 2016;34(3):2349-2570.
2. Duke-Elder S, Leigh AG. Disease of the outer eye. In: *system of ophthalmology.* Duke-Elder

S (ed). London: Henry Kimpton Publ. 1985; 57 3-585.

3. Krachmer J. 2nd ed. 2005;1481.
4. Kenyon K, Wagoner M, Hettinger M. Conjunctival Autograft Transplantation for Advanced and Recurrent Pterygium. *Ophthalmology* 1985;92(11):1461-1470.
5. Koranyi G, Seregard S, Kopp E. The cut-and-paste method for primary pterygium surgery: long-term follow-up. *Acta Ophthalmologica Scandinavica.* 2005;83(3):298-301.
6. Koranyi G. Cut and paste: a no suture, small incision approach to pterygium surgery. *British Journal of Ophthalmology.* 2004;88(7):911-914.
7. Malik K, Goel R, Gupta A, Gupta S, Kamal S, Malik V et al. Efficacy of suture less and glue free limbal conjunctival autograft for primary pterygium surgery. *Nepalese Journal of Ophthalmology,* 2012; 4(2).
8. Chaudhary S, Dutta J, Mukhopadhyay S et al. Comparison of autologous in situ blood coagulum versus sutures for conjunctival autografting after pterygium excision. *Int Ophthalmol.* 2014;34(1):41-48.